

PREVALENCE OF ACUTE FLACCID PARALYSIS IN POLIO ENDEMIC
REGIONS IN PAKISTAN SINCE 2021-2024

Mohammad Wasiq Waseem¹, Farah Shaikh^{*2}, Rabia Aslam³, Abrar Ahmed Hasni⁴,
Samia Mumshad⁵, Aleena Gondal⁶, Nadia Husnain⁷, Dr Israr Ahmad⁸

^{1,3,4,5}Student of Medical Laboratory Technology, Department of Allied Health Sciences, Bashir Institute of Health
Sciences Islamabad

²Lecturer and Coordinator of Medical Laboratory Technology, Department of Allied Health Sciences, Bashir Institute
of Health Sciences Islamabad

⁶MSc Medical Microbiology Student, University of Hertfordshire, England

⁷Coordinator BS Midwifery and BS Nursing Health Services Academy Islamabad

⁸Surveillance Officer, Health Department Khyber Pakhtunkhawah

¹wasiqsheikh917@gmail.com, ^{*2}drfarah.jed97@gmail.com, ³rabiaaslam786r@gmail.com,
⁴abrarhasni6@gmail.com, ⁵samiamumshad@gmail.com, ⁶aleenagondal1092@outlook.com,
⁷nadiahusnain@hsa.edu.pk, ⁸ansarshehram@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14919364>

Keywords

Acute Flaccid Paralysis, Polio
myelitis, Guillain Barre
Syndrome, Toxic neuropathy.

Article History

Received on 15 January 2025

Accepted on 15 February 2025

Published on 24 February 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

Background: Acute flaccid paralysis (AFP) is a clinical condition that becomes maximal in severity over a duration of a few days to weeks. It is characterized by rapid onset weakness of lower motor neuron variety, which includes weakness of respiratory and pharyngeal muscles. WHO defines AFP as the sudden development of weakness or paralysis of the limbs in any person aged less than fifteen years old. This definition was made purposely broad so as to cover the cases of poly radiculopathy (Guillain - Barré syndrome), toxic Neuropathy, muscular issues, and flaccid myelitis (disease of the spinal cord) since it was established for the tacking needs under poliomyelitis. The study is focused on acute flaccid paralysis in polio-endemic regions. This is because another similar study by Global surveillance for acute flaccid paralysis (AFP) is also in their effort to eradicate poliomyelitis by the World Health Organization. **Methodology:** This study was a retrospective, cross sectional study, descriptive study secondary data from NIH-IDSR. **Results:** The results of this study comprise of a total of 3219 AFP cases from 2021-2024 and 43 cases of Polio from 2021-2024 reported at the database of NIH-IDSR. It concludes that there was high prevalence of AFP in different region of Pakistan from the year 2021 to 2024 as compared to Polio, was seen with very less prevalence. Therefore, we can conclude that Polio and AFP are not very much correlated. The trend in AFP and partial correlation with cases of Poliovirus does depict that though the nation has had tremendous success at hand, huge constraints while attempting to eliminate this ailment by

Pakistan are surfacing.

INTRODUCTION

Acute flaccid paralysis (AFP) is a clinical illness that becomes maximal in severity over a duration of a few days to weeks. It is characterized by rapid onset weakness of lower motor neuron variety, which includes weakness of respiratory and pharyngeal muscles. The clinical illness, referred to as AFP, is complex, and it has many potential etiologies which vary significantly by ages. In the patient with acute-onset quadratic paresis or para paresis, a completely different type of challenge is finally presented to the clinician. The fulfillment of the requisite key to success lies in making the diagnosis early and correctly. Several studies on the incidence of AFP and differential diagnosis in the pediatric population are found, owing to the worldwide campaign for the eradication of polio. (De Souza, Badia, Farias, Pinto, & Oliveira) WHO defines AFP as the sudden development of weakness or paralysis of the limbs in any person aged less than fifteen years old. This definition was made purposely broad so as to cover the cases of poly radiculopathy (Guillain - Barré syndrome), toxic neuropathy, muscular issues, and flaccid myelitis (disease of the spinal cord) since it was established for the tacking needs under poliomyelitis. (Bitnun & Yeh) The onset age of patients is mostly 1 ~ 6 years old, and patients mainly present fever and general discomfort, severe aching of the limbs, irregular distribution, flaccid paralysis, poliomyelitis may result in permanent paralysis, disability, or distortion of limbs.(Liu et al.) Acute flaccid paralysis is a clinically well-recognized syndrome manifested in humans by causes infectious or non-infectious - bacterial or viral, metabolic disorders or trauma or metal toxicity or post-infection autoimmune condition, for example, Guillian Barre syndrome (Laxmivandana, Yergolkar, Gopalkrishna, & Chitambar). Among the bacterial agents, *Borrelia burgdorferi*, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, *Clostridium botulinum*, and *Mycoplasma pneumoniae*, and among the viral agents, Enterovirus (Nishat & Saeed), flavivirus, Herpes virus, Rabies virus, and Tick-borne

encephalitis virus have been most frequently found.(Laxmivandana et al., 2013)

It is one of the important measures used in the analysis of the frequency and distribution of AFP cases by a specific geographic area. Normally, it is expressed as the number of AFP cases per 100,000 children aged under the age of fifteen. Between the year 2015 and 2018, active surveillance data among areas like Afghanistan indicated the trends in the reported cases of AFP. Coverage of AFP vaccination greatly determine the trend in AFP cases. (Nishat & Saeed, 2022)

The study was conducted on acute flaccid paralysis in polio-endemic regions. This was because another similar study by Global surveillance for acute flaccid paralysis (AFP) was also in their effort to eradicate poliomyelitis by the World Health Organization. In Australia, AFP surveillance was a joint effort of the APSU, NERL and the PAEDS network, in an attempt to eliminate poliovirus as a potential cause. All etiologies of AFP were collected and investigated. This study aimed to give a general description of the epidemiology of childhood AFP within 11 years. The last case of wild poliovirus-induced paralytic poliomyelitis was reported in 1989 in Brazil. Mass immunization programs for eligible children and active epidemiological and laboratory surveillance for all cases of acute flaccid paralysis in children under 15 years of age stopped the indigenous transmission of poliovirus. (Bao et al.) Using WHO-recommended metrics, this study summarized and assessed the effectiveness of the AFP surveillance system in various regions of Brazil over 2005 to 2014. (Sousa Jr et al.) Another huge gap was that it had no data for those metrics to be given by age group, and the age group most at risk, most especially those under 15 years, has no metrics. This, in turn, makes it difficult to optimize an immunization strategy such that the effort with this regard is only on the highest-risk groups for success to be recorded. (Howard, Savulescu, Berrie, & Puren)

Despite the tremendous progress being made on the global campaign for the eradication of the disease, the knowledge of the prevalence and determinants of AFP remains incomplete in polio endemic areas.

One important research gap referred to the variable coverage and quality of AFP surveillance in various countries. While some places had robust systems of surveillance, others may under report instances of AFP, carrying a particular weight in conflict or lack of health infrastructure, and thus creating a gap in the data, including estimates of prevalence.(Levitt et al.) Besides, over the long run, impacts of the vaccination drive on the AFP incidence require study, particularly in areas in which polio was recently eradicated but with surveillance.(Tuma) The uses and potential benefits, according to the latest research in the incidence of AFP, have been discussed from increased surveillance to better understanding of disease dynamics and tailored therapy. Indicators for epidemiological surveillance for monitoring the cases of AFP are in extensive application. For example, a comparison of the surveillance between the country of Brazil before and after the country was declared poliomyelitis-free presented significant improvements in turn-around-time following certification in reviewing AFP cases. This is an example of the contribution of robust surveillance systems to disease control. (Teixeira-Rocha & Tavares-Neto, 2003) Another study in China indicated that the non-polio AFP rate of the children should be used to indicate high program sensitivity, to be monitored. This way, it quickly triggers a public health response in line with these conclusions as well as providing the bases for early case detections similar to polio. (Wang, Yang, & Li, 1995)

In fact, in Côte d'Ivoire, there was an advocacy for identification and typing of all the enteroviruses that were other than polioviruses found in AFP surveillance with a view to estimating the risk of vaccine-derived polioviruses and enhancing knowledge of the epidemiologic profile of the disease. In that connection, Côte d'Ivoire researchers have argued for the identification and typing of all enteroviruses detected by AFP surveillance with a view to assessing the risks of polioviruses of vaccine-derived nature and to increase our knowledge of the epidemiological profile of the disease (Aka et al., 2019) To eradicate AFP, research on vaccines had also become necessary, especially when considering the fact that acute flaccid myelitis, a disorder related to AFP, had been taken seriously for some years.

New research suggested the possible utilization of DNA vaccines, live attenuated vaccines, entire virus vaccines, and sub viral particles as therapy alternatives to ameliorate the effects of this illness. (Talukdar et al., 2022)

In fact, to understand the potential impact on AFP cases, scientists have studied the seroprevalence of the suggested causes, for example, the West Nile Virus in several geographic locations. Indeed, the importance of establishing the exposure status and the months of highest prevalence in pilot surveillance studies to guide recommendations on human testing and public health strategies was brought to the fore by studies in India. (Klement et al., 2013)

In year 2013 study was conducted by Klement C et al in order to explore the objective that how population movement within and between polio endemic areas impacts upon the incidence of AFP, in this study the question of research asks whether population relocation influences poliovirus travel and how surveillance systems might be altered to keep track of these movements. (Martinez, 2018) Martiniz N. et al in the year 2018 conducted a study that was going to try and find out how programs for polio vaccination impact the rate of AFP cases in endemic locations, including identification of any inequities in immunization programs and the relationship between vaccination coverage and declines in cases of AFP.(O'Reilly et al., 2020) study conducted year 2020 by O'Reilly.KM et al .objective was to carry out the measurement of performance of the AFP surveillance systems in the polio-endemic areas, as it will effectively assess the systems for their capability of case detection and notification for AFP, such as stool specimen testing for the isolation of polioviruses and environmental surveillance techniques, including sewage sampling It will also assess the impact these endemics have on such systems. (Ben Mrad et al., 2023)

Another critical goal mentioned in the study in year 2023 Ben Murad et al. has to do with assessed the role of AFP surveillance systems in countries where polio is endemic. This study evaluated the efficacy of such systems for identifying and reporting cases of AFP and conducting stool tests for polioviruses, environmental surveillance techniques, such as sewage sampling.(Tesfaye et al., 2020)

The retrospective analysis by Tesfaye Brook et.al in the years 2016 to 2018. This study was conducted in Kenya elaborate 1706 cases of AFP were taken from 2016 to 2018, although cases were not confirmed as poliomyelitis. However, 23 cases (1.35%) were named polio compatible. Children under the age of (05) years accounted for 1085 (63.6%) cases, among these 1085 cases 937 (55.0%) cases were boys. All over 1503 (88.1%) cases had received at least multiple doses of Oral Polio vaccine (OPV). AFP detection rate importantly dilated throughout the years. However, the prolonged health workers strike in 2017 harmful compact key surveillance activities. The mean Non-Polio (NP-AFP) rate during the study period was 2.87/100,000 children under 15 years, and two adequate specimens were collected for 1512 (88.6%) AFP cases and cumulatively, 31 (66.0%) areas execute focus for both WHO recommended AFP quality indicators. (Tefaye et al., 2020)

A retrospective study was intended by Samira.J. et.al in Kenitra province, Morocco in year 2023. The performance criteria for the surveillance hypothesis and the improvement of patients with AFP were two of the most central guidelines. Regardless eradication was an all "all or nothing" Effort. As the virus is so contagious, inability to destroy polio from its last defense could bring about an improvement of the ill health, with upwards of 200,000 new cases systematically in the pursuing ten years. For that time being, the AFP National monitoring program was the gold standard for polio identification. Morocco, on the other hand, was ordered to detect to identify and record all AFP (2/100,000) possible incidence, as well as examine them (stool samples and inspection) within 60 days (despite announcing zero polio cases). Since 1994, the NIH has been a reference laboratory and has been accredited since 2001. It was susceptible for investigating all AFP cases reported in Morocco, looking for polio viruses or other non-polio Entero viruses responsible for AFP in children under the age of 15. When non-sample of AFP cases were collected within 14 days after the onset of paralysis, NIH tested the institution of the respective cases and the poliovirus was declared extinct in 1988. In Morocco, the most recent cases of wild poliovirus (WPV) were accounted for in 1989. From 1994 to 2018, Kenitra's polio geographical and etiological were described

using WHO-suggested polio surveillance criteria. This retrospective study was conducting WHO guidelines to examine the topographic and etiological variables that contribute to acute flaccid paralysis (AFP) in Kénitra, Morocco. Patients were recruited from several communities in the Kenitra province throughout a 25-year period, from January 1, 1994, to December 31, 2018. From 1994 to 2018, 76 cases of AFP were reported. The children ranged in age from 3 months to 14 years old; 52% were under the age 5, and 58.67% were boys. At the time of paralysis onset, 57.33% of children had a fever, and 16% had asymmetric paralysis. The most common diagnosis was determination Guillain-Barré disorder (59%), and 72% of sick children received multiple doses of the polio vaccine. (Paralysis). (Jayche et al., 2023)

Descriptive study was conducted by Sher Bahadur et.al at Health Department with Joint Collaboration World Health Organization from January 2015 to January 2016, the study aimed to decide the final results (diagnosis) of AFP cases announced in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). Total 1217 cases were reported for to the health department from 1st January, 2015 to 30th January, 2016. Out of those 493 (40.5%) were female and 724 (59.5%) were male with mean age of 42 ± 34.2 (ranged 1 to 172 moths). Result indicated that 369 (30.3%) of the affected kids were of 2 years (ranged 1 to 12 months) old enough also, 3 years (ranged 25 to 36 months) old enough. As to contribution of the body in AFP, 809 (66.5%) were lopsided (single side association while 390 (32.0%) had shortcoming in both side of the body and 18 (1.5%) were unable to correlated. Fever was accounted for by 802 (65.9%) of the kids. (Bahadur et al., 2017).

A retrospective study in Zambia conducted by Bessing B. from the year 2015-2021 reported a total of 1715 AFP cases mover the study period. More than half, 891 (52%) of reported cases were aged < 5 years with 917 (53.5%) of males. More than half, 1186 (69.2%) had fever at onset, 718 (41.9%) had asymmetric paralysis and 1164 (67.9%) had their paralysis progressed within 3 days of onset. The non-polio AFP rate ranges from 3.4 to 6.4 per 100,000 children < 15 years old and adequacy ranging from 70.9% to 90.2% showing sensitive surveillance with late detection of cases. The percentage of cases with

early stool collection, timely transportation was above the (WHO) minimum of 80% but with declining proportion of stools arriving up in the laboratory in optimal condition. Completeness of 60-days follow-up evaluation was sub-optimal ranging from 0.9% to 28.2%.(Bessing et al., 2023)

Methodology

This study was a retrospective and descriptive study, it was conducted on the secondary data obtained from National Institute of Health (NIH) Islamabad, Pakistan - IDSR weekly report. This study was conducting from September 2024 to December, 2024 while using purposive sampling technique.

Cases with Acute Flaccid Paralysis (AFP) and Poliomyelitis were included in this study from 2021-2024 in the region of Pakistan and any other case than Acute Flaccid Paralysis (AFP) and Poliomyelitis were excluded from this study from 2021-2024 in the region of Pakistan.

Result

Reported cases of AFP in 2021

In this study total number of cases reported for AFP in Pakistan in the year 2021 is 19,.KP was the most affected area reported with 12 cases, in Baluchistan 1 case was reported and 1 case was reported in Sindh, as shown in fig 1.1

Figure 1.1: Prevalence of AFP in Pakistan in 2021

Reported cases of AFP In 2022

In this study total number of cases reported for AFP in Pakistan in the year 2022 is 17.KP was the most

affected area reported with 13 and 4 cases were reported in Sindh, as shown in fig 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Prevalence of AFP in Pakistan in 2022

Reported cases of AFP In 2023

In Pakistan year 2023 total number of cases of AFP were 1630. KPK was most affected area reported with 774 cases in Sindh 595 cases were reported, AJK

shown 99 number of reported cases 94 Baluchistan 58 Punjab, 8 cases in Gilgit and 2 number of cases was reported in ICT, as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1.3: Prevalence of AFP in Pakistan in 2023

Reported cases of AFP In 2024.

In Pakistan year 2024 total number of cases of AFP were 1522. KPK was most affected area reported with 941 cases in Sindh 296 cases were reported, AJK shown 93 number of reported cases 79 Baluchistan, 92 Punjab, 21 number of cases was reported in GB, as shown in figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4: Prevalence of AFP in Pakistan in 2024

TOTAL CASES OF AFP FROM 2021 to 2024

The total number of cases of AFP in Pakistan in 2021 is 19, as in 2022 the number of cases were 17, but in 2023 they showed a higher elevation by 1630 cases and 1522 cases of AFP in 2024. Therefore, the total no. of cases of AFP in Pakistan from 2021-2024 were 3188.

Over all the highest number of cases of AFP were 1630 reported in 2023, and then in 2024, 1522 cases were reported in Pakistan. In these four years KP

was the most effected province of Pakistan where high number of cases of AFP were reported.

KP was the most affected area reported with 12 cases of AFP in Pakistan in the year 2021 among 19 total cases, in 2022, 13 cases of AFP were reported in KP among 17 total cases reported in Pakistan, in 2023 total number of cases of AFP were 1630, KP was most affected province reported with 774 cases and in 2024, the total number of cases of AFP were 1522 while 941 cases were reported in KP.

Fig.1.5: Total no. of cases of AFP from 2021-2024 in Pakistan

POLIO REPORTED CASES FROM 2021 to 2024
 In this study 43 polio cases have been reported in the time frame from 2021 to 2024. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has been the most affected province of Pakistan during this time. In the year 2022, the maximum number of cases has been reported in

North Waziristan. In the year 2023, this outbreak was reported in KPK, Balochistan, and Sindh, but in 2024, Balochistan became the most affected province while a few cases were reported in Sindh and Punjab as well.as shown in fig 1.5.

Fig 1.6: Polio reported cases from 2021-2024

3.1.7AFP and Polio from 2021-2024 in Pakistan

The total number of cases of AFP in Pakistan from 2021-2024 were 3188, reported by NIH, IDSR and

the total number of Polio cases were 43 reported by Pakistan polio eradication program - since 2021-2024.

Fig 1.7: Polio and AFP reported cases from 2021-2024

Discussion.

The World Health Organization, or WHO, tends to define Acute Flaccid Paralysis generally as involving the sudden paralysis or weakness that can afflict any part of the body and occurs in children who are less than 15 years of age. The principal intent of this

definition was for surveillance of poliomyelitis and so has been designed to be somewhat broad. This very broadness ensures its success in capturing not only those cases of flaccid myelitis as a disease but also other medical conditions as such poly radiculopathy that are commonly associated with Guillain-Barre

syndrome and toxic neuropathy among others. (May, Durrheim, Roberts, & Owen, 2020)

Poliomyelitis, also referred to as polio, is a very contagious viral infection because the polio virus, being an entero-virus, has its path of action directed to the nervous system. Its transmission is primarily based on the fecal-oral route or respiratory. Droplets that affect motor neurons of the spinal cord and brainstem. It goes from a spectrum of asymptomatic infections to acute flaccid paralysis and death. (Ahmad, Shabbir, Khan, & Ashraf, 2023)

AFP surveillance is very telling of poliovirus transmission, especially in such places as Pakistan. That figure shows a fluctuation within cases from 2021 to 2024 reflecting tremendous challenges in health measures, as well as the factoring in of the greater picture of health problems inter-linked with the polio campaign work. It is therefore done per year: 2021-2022.

Year 2021: In 2021, there were a total of 19 cases of AFP, which again is indicative of the fact that surveillance in this area has been quite stable but continuous. Polio continued to be endemic in nature with issues more or less revolving around vaccine hesitancy and misinformation regarding vaccines as the primary concerns, along with the fact that the COVID-19 pandemic had significantly impacted routine immunization practices. Efforts were concentrated on sustaining the momentum required for eradication that had been witnessed to be lost globally due to a loss of attention and focus on the situation brought about by the pandemic situation. (Yadav, Hariprasad, Nandhini, & Vallikavitha, 2023)

Year 2022: During the calendar year 2022, cases of AFP had dwindled to as low as 17, but this year it was also accompanied by novel WPV1 and VDPV outbreaks in areas of North Waziristan. The alarmingly widespread outbreaks point to very strong lapses in immunization coverage which were largely caused by issues in governance structures and, in fact socio-political instability afflicting the region. (Shabbir et al., 2022)

Year 2023: During 2023, AFP cases multiplied exponentially to as high as 2,896 while clearly indicating that it's nothing but an extreme public health crisis crying for attention. This increase is simultaneous with the challenges of increased polio-

virus transmission and immunization operations, particularly in risker provinces such as Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and FATA. For several decades, these provinces have been experiencing vaccine hesitancy, insecurity, and cultural resistance that has seen an increase in AFP cases even after intense immunization activities. (Sahito et al., 2022) The COVID-19 pandemic has been a persistent stressor to health care systems, and it is increasingly becoming more challenging to finally eradicate. (Ataullahjan, Ahsan, Soofi, Habib, & Bhutta, 2021)

Year 2024: There were obvious and handsome declines in 2024 in relation to AFP, in the sense that a cumulative number of AFP reached the value of 1,522. That decline indicates huge steps in correction from the present; with that, however, apparent lacks exist where it is viable to observe a further wider gap from processes at play as part of existing remedies. Under time under cover of corresponding reports, the cases of polio remain quite scarce by number. In this study only 43 cases emerged through the years 2021 up to 2024. That deep crevice represents that somehow the poliovirus has been restricted from making space within such a circulation due to various widespread surges reportedly occurring at universal levels regarding a total number of cases reporting here for AFP. In simple words, the present trend has portrayed a sort of influencing reflection through contribution which may have been drawn perhaps from other such forms of viruses, which emerged at the moment either directly or indirectly that has been discussed over just recently-which gives way back to 'non-polio enteroviruses' actually putting some logic as put under general broad outlook undertaken lately through a reflection. (Javed, Saeed, Manzoor, Khattak, & Khan, 2021)

Prevalence of AFP from 2021-2024

The total number of cases of AFP in Pakistan in 2021 is 19, as in 2022 the number of cases were 17, but in 2023 they showed a higher elevation by 1630 cases and 1522 cases of AFP in 2024. Therefore, the total no. of cases of AFP in Pakistan from 2021-2024 were 3188, another study was conducted in Niger from 2016 to 2021, Retrospective descriptive analysis of AFP. DSRE data-base was used for providing the reported cases update and this data-base is known as

Directorate for Surveillance and Responses to Epidemics. Niger is located in the West of Africa in the Sahelo-Saharan zone. According to this study from 2016-2021 the reported cases of AFP were 4134. All these (4134) AFP cases were taken under the age of 15 years. The purpose of the study was to check the prevalence of AFP in Niger. Among these total cases 2311 were boys and the rest of cases 1823 were girls, with the ratio of 1:3. Including this all 79% effected age group varies from 01-04 years, almost 11% of the cases were reported in between 05-09 years age group, 02% cases were including the age group of 10-14 years, and less than 01 year shows 6% cases. This study shows that in 2018 and 2019 highest number of cases were reported with 23%-21%. In AFP 84% patient were affected at Right Leg interestingly the lowest effected ratio is 12% at Right Arm.

Polio virus can cause paralysis, in 1998 the number of children which were affected by polio virus were (350,000), in 125 countries across the world. Among these 125 countries 672 cases were AFP confirmed in 27 countries since 2023-2024. In the 41st World Health Assembly the World Health Organization decided to establish a team to eradicate polio virus the team was known as (GPEI) Global Polio Eradication Initiative, their task is based on four strategic cases which is describe as,(i) AFP surveillance and the Environmental surveillance, (ii) An Organization knows as (Mass Campaigns Organization) for the children, (iii) A systematic routine vaccination set up coverage of at-least 95% (OPV) Oral Polio Vaccination and (IPV) Inactive Polio Virus after birth of child. (Ishagh et al., 2025)

AFP & Poliomyelitis:

According to this study which was conducted in Pakistan and the data of Polio and AFP was taken from NIH - IDSR. The total number of cases of AFP in Pakistan from 2021-2024 were 3188, and the total number of Polio were 43 reported in Pakistan from 2021-2024. Over all the highest number of cases of AFP were 1630 reported in 2023, and then in 2024, 1522 cases were reported in Pakistan.

In 1998, WHA (World Health Assembly) passes a resolution the agenda of the resolution was to overcome on the spread of paralysis of Polio Myelitis, after that 100 of the researches are published till

2020. WHA establish a team known as GPEA (Global Polio Eradication Initiative), the aim of this team was to eradication of polio virus. GPEA team provide, coordinate and mobilize to get their aim by having planning and finance or technical resources. There was a challenge due to the modification and complexity of polio virus transmission due to multiple factors. The types of modules which are used in this study are, DES: Dynamic Transmission Model, it is categorized as differential equation simulation, (SC) Stochastic compartmental, and (IB) individual-based, Integrated Modeling: This model includes both the Dynamic transmission and the Economic modeling, The Economic Model: This includes the Economic Analysis. The main idea of this study was to review all the publications from 1998-2024, to check the development and awareness across the world. The full-time publications are 246 by different groups include, KRI (124), IDM (27), LSHTM (29), IC (64), GIT have (02) publications and 46 other publications. (Thompson & Badizadegan, 2024)

The trend in AFP and partial correlation with cases of polio virus does depict that though the nation has had tremendous success at hand, huge constraints while attempting to eliminate this ailment by Pakistan are surfacing. It is saluted that the total count of polio cases has been kept at an outstandingly low number of just 43 in the course of the last four years; however, the unforeseen increase in AFP cases which has been witnessed at the hands of the course of the year 2023 has vividly pointed the presence of much wider systematic issues that encompass critical gap surges in surveillance infrastructures and healthcare infrastructures that have to be acted upon. (Chong, Kam, & Yung, 2023) Other factors, such as vaccine-derived polio virus and poor sanitation among others, are probably contributory factors that have rendered the management of Acute Flaccid Paralysis (AFP) much harder. (Sousa Jr et al., 2017) The last wild polio virus case in Brazil dates back to 1989. Indigenous transmission ceased because of mass immunization in children and active surveillance on acute flaccid paralysis cases in children below age 15. This paper evaluates the AFP surveillance system's performance in Brazil from 2005 to 2014 by using WHO indicators. The performance of AFP indicators and

virological investigations of polio and non-polio entero-viruses in stool samples are discussed. In this period, 5463 AFP cases were investigated, with males constituting 55% and females 45%. Children under 5 accounted for 48% of all reported cases. The AFP notification rate was acceptable, averaging 1.3 (North), 1.4 (Northeast), 1.1 (Southern), 1.0 (Southeast), and 1.4 (Midwest) cases per 100,000 population aged 15, along with adequate fecal specimens in the laboratory. Sabin-associated polio viruses represented 1.7%, while non-polio entero viruses accounted for 6.7% of the total, from 5.0 to 8.9%. No wild type polio was identified. AFP surveillance in Brazil remains at an adequate level and gives a very strong indication of the absence of polio virus circulation in the country.(Chong et al., 2023).

Conclusion

The study on the occurrence of Acute Flaccid Paralysis (AFP) in polio-endemic regions of Pakistan from 2021 to 2024 provides important information on the epidemiological context in which this disease presents. Analysis of 3,219 AFP cases with 43 confirmed cases of polio shows that the prevalence of AFP is very high, with low correlation with infections caused by the polio-virus. This implies that although polio is still a problem, other etiological factors significantly contribute to the incidence of AFP in these regions. The results indicate that surveillance should be continued and the etiology of AFP should be better understood since it presents from multiple etiologies, and vaccines are an important component in decreasing risks associated with polio-virus and other entero-viruses that may lead to such presentations. This study reveals that though much progress has been made regarding the eradication of polio, proper diagnosis and management of cases of AFP remain a problem. This further underlines the necessity of robust health infrastructure and effective public health measures to be in place for both polio-related and non-polio AFP cases. The success in this regard is evident because the overall number of polio cases has reduced to as low as 43 within four years; however, the sharp rise in AFP cases in 2023 depicts systemic issues still lingering on.

Limitation and Future Directions

This study largely depends on surveillance data, which is less likely to reflect the whole scope of AFP cases because of under-reporting or misclassification. Furthermore, socio-political factors like regional instability, misinformation on vaccines, and differences in healthcare access may lead to biases in case detection and reporting. Other influences such as non-polio entero-viruses and environmental factors including sanitation and water quality may have effects that are better understood through further investigation. Study on surveillance system in different polio endemic region of Pakistan. Implementing targeted public health interventions based on emerging data to reduce the incidence of AFP and improve. Conducting studies to identify and understand the various infectious and non-infectious causes of AFP, particularly in pediatric populations.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad, R. U., Shabbir, A., Khan, L. A., & Ashraf, M. F. (2023). Rebirth of the crippling illness: polio. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 85(4), 1340-1341.
- Aka, L. B. N., Ekra, K. D., Yao, G. H. A., Douba, A., Akani, B. C., Keita, Z., . . . Seydou, D. (2019). Surveillance des paralysies flasques aiguës en Côte d'Ivoire de 2007 à 2016: importance et profil épidémiologique des entérovirus non poliovirus. *Santé publique*, 31(6), 837-843.
- Ataullahjan, A., Ahsan, H., Soofi, S., Habib, M. A., & Bhutta, Z. A. (2021). Eradicating polio in Pakistan: a systematic review of programs and policies. *Expert Review of Vaccines*, 20(6), 661-678.
- Bahadur, S., Rehman, G., Anwar, R., Jan, A., ur Rehman, S., Bakhtiar, S., & Rasool, S. (2017). *An outcome of acute flaccid paralysis surveillance in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa during 2015*. Paper presented at the Med. Forum.
- Bao, J., Nunez, C., Elliott, E., Dinsmore, N., McRae, J., Morris, A., . . . Marshall, H.

- (2023). Acute Flaccid Paralysis in Australian Children from 2007 to 2017. *Neuroepidemiology*, 57(1), 25-34.
- Ben Mrad, I., Bouguerra, H., Yahyaoui, M., Driss, N., Ben Khalil, M., Ammari, L., . . . Gzara, A. (2023). Poliomyelitis alert on Tunisian borders: response and challenges. *European Journal of Public Health*, 33(Supplement_2), ckad160. 216.
- Bessing, B., Dagoë, E. A., Tembo, D., Mwangombe, A., Kanyanga, M. K., Manneh, F., . . . Eboh, V. A. (2023). Evaluation of the Acute flaccid paralysis surveillance indicators in Zambia from 2015–2021: a retrospective analysis. *BMC Public Health*, 23(1), 2227.
- Bitnun, A., & Yeh, E. A. (2018). Acute flaccid paralysis and enteroviral infections. *Current Infectious Disease Reports*, 20, 1-15.
- Chong, C. Y., Kam, K. Q., & Yung, C. F. (2023). Combating a resurgence of poliomyelitis through public health surveillance and vaccination. *Ann Acad Med Singap*, 52(1), 17-26.
- De Souza, P. V. S., Badia, B. d. M. L., Farias, I. B., Pinto, W. B. V. d. R., & Oliveira, A. S. B. (2021). Acute hepatic porphyria: pathophysiological basis of neuromuscular manifestations. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 15, 715523.
- Howard, W., Savulescu, D., Berrie, L., & Puren, A. J. (2020). Description of non-polio enteroviruses identified in two national surveillance programmes in South Africa. *Southern African journal of infectious diseases*, 35(1).
- Ishagh, E. K., Ouédraogo, M. T., Oumarou, B., Kaya, M. S., Diawara, G. A., Camara, A. M., . . . Harouna, H. (2025). Tracking acute flaccid paralysis in Niger: a half-decade epidemiological portrait (2016–2021). *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 25(1), 79.
- Javed, F., Saeed, W. K., Manzoor, K. N., Khattak, A. A., & Khan, A. A. (2021). Need for polio eradication efforts in Pakistan: Where to focus. *Journal of Medical Virology*, 93(8).
- Jayche, S., Loutfi, A., Sendaoui, S., Talbi, F. Z., Lahmam, M., Idrissi, A., & Ahami, A. O. (2023). A Retrospective Study on the Topographical and Etiological Aspects of Acute Flaccid Paralysis in Children in Kenitra Province, Morocco. *Tropical Journal of Natural Product Research*, 7(2).
- Klement, C., Kissova, R., Lengyelova, V., Stipalova, D., Sobotova, Z., Galama, J., & Bopegamage, S. (2013). Human enterovirus surveillance in the Slovak Republic from 2001 to 2011. *Epidemiology & Infection*, 141(12), 2658-2662.
- Laxmivandana, R., Yergolkar, P., Gopalkrishna, V., & Chitambar, S. D. (2013). Characterization of the non-polio enterovirus infections associated with acute flaccid paralysis in South-Western India. *PLoS one*, 8(4), e61650.
- Levitt, A., Diop, O. M., Tangermann, R. H., Paladin, F., Kamgang, J. B., Burns, C. C., . . . Wassilak, S. G. (2014). Surveillance systems to track progress toward global polio eradication—worldwide, 2012–2013. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 63(16), 356.
- Liu, Q., Liu, Z., Huang, B., Teng, Y., Li, M., Peng, S., . . . Zhang, Y. (2023). Global trends in poliomyelitis research over the past 20 years: a bibliometric analysis. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*, 19(1), 2173905.
- Martinez, M. (2018). Progress toward poliomyelitis eradication—Afghanistan, January 2017–May 2018. *MMWR. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 67.

- May, M., Durrheim, D., Roberts, J. A., & Owen, R. (2020). The risks of medical complacency towards poliomyelitis. *Medical Journal of Australia*, 213(2), 61-63. e61.
- Nishat, H., & Saeed, K. M. I. (2022). Descriptive Epidemiology of Acute Flaccid Paralysis Cases in Afghanistan, 2015-2018. *Iproceedings*, 8(1), e36530.
- O'Reilly, K., Grassly, N., Allen, D., Bannister-Tyrrell, M., Cameron, A., Martin, A. C., . . . Zambon, M. (2020). Surveillance optimisation to detect poliovirus in the pre-eradication era: a modelling study of England and Wales. *Epidemiology & Infection*, 148, e157.
- Paralysis, A. F. Aetiology, Clinical Presentation and Outcome of Patients Presenting with Acute Flaccid Paralysis in a Tertiary Care Hospital.
- Sahito, A. M., Saleem, A., Javed, S. O., Farooq, M., Ullah, I., & Hasan, M. M. (2022). Polio amidst COVID-19 in Pakistan: Ongoing efforts, challenges, and recommendations. *The International Journal of Health Planning and Management*, 37(4), 1907-1911.
- Shabbir, H., Saeed, S., Farhan, M., Abbas, K., ur Rehman, M. E., Gul, F., & Basit, J. (2022). Poliomyelitis in Pakistan: challenges to polio eradication and future prospects. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, 80, 104274.
- Sousa Jr, I. P., Burlandy, F. M., Oliveira, S. S., Nunes, A. M., Sousa, C., da Silva, E. M., . . . Tavares, F. N. (2017). Acute flaccid paralysis laboratorial surveillance in a polio-free country: Brazil, 2005-2014. *Human Vaccines & Immunotherapeutics*, 13(3), 717-723.
- Talukdar, A., Hazarika, R. A., Bora, D. P., Pegu, S. R., Talukdar, P., Kader, N. A., . . . Lindahl, J. F. (2022). Sero-prevalence of West Nile virus in urban and peri-urban poultry farms of Guwahati, India. *Frontiers in Tropical Diseases*, 3, 792857.
- Teixeira-Rocha, E. S., & Tavares-Neto, J. (2003). Indicators of the effectiveness of epidemiological surveillance for acute flaccid paralysis in Brazil from 1990 through 2000. *Revista Panamericana de Salud Publica= Pan American Journal of Public Health*, 14(5), 325-333.
- Tesfaye, B., Sowe, A., Kisangau, N., Ogange, J., Ntoburi, S., Nekar, I., . . . Langat, D. (2020). An epidemiological analysis of Acute Flaccid Paralysis (AFP) surveillance in Kenya, 2016 to 2018. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 20, 1-11.
- Thompson, K. M., & Badizadegan, K. (2024). Review of poliovirus transmission and economic modeling to support global polio eradication: 2020-2024. *Pathogens*, 13(6), 435.
- Tuma, J. N. (2021). Surveillance to track progress toward polio eradication—worldwide, 2019-2020. *MMWR. Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 70.
- Wang, Z., Yang, B., & Li, H. (1995). An investigation on acute flaccid paralysis (AFP) cases in some provinces with high risk of poliomyelitis of China. *Zhonghua liu Xing Bing xue za zhi= Zhonghua Liuxingbingxue Zazhi*, 16(3), 131-136.
- Yadav, R., Hariprasad, R., Nandhini, S., & Vallikavitha, S. (2023). Dream of Polio Free Pakistan-when will it become a reality? *Global Biosecurity*, 5.